

CREEP OF SiC-PLATELET REINFORCED ALUMINA

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ABSTRACT

Three types of SiC-platelet reinforced Al_2O_3 composites have been fabricated: via tape casting and lamination (T), via slip casting using an aqueous route (S), and via powder pressing of granulated tapes (P). Tape casting and lamination produces a strong anisotropy in the reinforcement orientation, whereas in the slip cast and powder pressed materials the reinforcement is more randomly oriented. The volume fraction of the platelets ranged from 0 to 30%. The composites were tested at 1250°C in flexure and compression under different loads. Significant differences in the creep behaviour were found between the S and T composites. The internal strains in the 30 vol% SiC composites were evaluated via neutron diffraction. The bending strains in the SiC were found to be higher in the S material than in the T one. TEM revealed a different in impurities on the samples depending on the processing route used to fabricate them. These impurities are very likely to affect the creep behaviour of the composites.

INTRODUCTION

The addition of SiC whiskers to an alumina matrix increases the high temperature creep resistance as compared with the monolith [1,2,3]. Based on this, the addition of SiC platelets to ceramic oxides has been suggested [4] as an alternative to whiskers since they may give rise to similar creep reducing mechanisms. Platelets are an attractive alternative due to their ease of processing and lower price as compared with whiskers, together with not having the health concerns associated to the asbestos-like geometry of whiskers[5]. In this study, the influence of various processing routes on the creep behaviour of pure alumina and alumina-SiC-platelet-reinforced composites was investigated. The green processing can affect the morphology of the platelet network, the internal stresses in the composites, the minor contaminants present, and the presence of a glassy phase at SiC- Al_2O_3 boundaries.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

PROCESSING

All composites were fabricated using Alcoa alumina A16-SG powder and C-Axis Technology Ltd. SiC-SF platelets. The compositions made were 0, 5, 15 and 30 vol% SiC. Different reinforcement network morphologies were achieved by fabricating the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}$ platelet composites via three different green processing routes: a) tape casting and lamination (T), b) tape casting, granulating and powder pressing (P), and c) slip casting, granulating, and powder pressing (S). These processes are described next.

Tape casting and lamination, T: In this process a standard slip formulation was used. Slips contained 25vol.% ceramic powder content. Details of the process have been described elsewhere [6]. Laminates were made by thermocompressing (at around 100°C) the required number of layers for a given thickness. This was followed by the binder burn out of the plastics. Tape casting, granulating and powder pressing, P: The green tapes were produced as described above. Then, they were heated to 600°C , to remove plasticisers and binders, leaving fragile tapes that were easily granulated into agglomerates ranging from 30 to $200\mu\text{m}$ in diameter which were then cold pressed to form the green body. Slip casting, granulating and powder pressing (S): The green processing was very similar to that used by Porter [7] for SiC whisker-reinforced alumina. Each phase was dispersed in aqueous slurries. A high pH (10-11) was used to disperse SiC and a low pH (2-3) to disperse alumina. They were then combined in the proportions necessary to achieve the reinforcement volume fraction desired and a pH neutral slurry containing alumina and SiC agglomerates was formed. This slurry was slip cast, allowed to dry, and then granulated into 50- $100\mu\text{m}$ diameter particles. As before, this powder was cold pressed to form the green body.

Figure 1. Optical micrographs of alumina 30vol%SiC platelet composites, a)T, b)P, c)S. The hot-pressing direction is vertical.

The green processing was followed by hot-pressing in a graphite die under vacuum for one hour. This was done at different temperatures to achieve a matrix grain size of 2-2.7 μm for the different compositions and a density of $\geq 98\%$ theoretical density. The microstructures achieved for 30vol% SiC are shown in figure 1. The tape cast and laminated sample (T) shows a strong anisotropy in the alignment of the platelets. The granulated tape sample (P) shows domains of similarly oriented platelets, since the granules came from oriented tapes. The slip cast (S) sample shows more randomly oriented platelets.

The preferential orientation of the platelets is such that the (0001) planes are perpendicular to the hot-pressing direction. The texture of the 30 vol% SiC composites was evaluated by x-ray diffraction. As the majority of the platelets¹ are of the 4H polytype, specimens were positioned in the diffractometer so that aligned platelets (perpendicular to the hot-pressing axis) were at the relevant angle to give diffraction, i.e. 2θ for the (0004) planes. By tilting the specimen away from this angle and measuring the x-ray intensity, the distribution of platelet orientations could be assessed. The normalised intensity of the (0004) diffraction peak versus the tilt angle was plotted as illustrated in figure 2 for the 30vol%SiC composites. Substantial alignment was achieved by the tape casting and laminating (T) method as compared with the other two composites (P and S) fabricated by granulating and powder pressing. From neutron diffraction texture analysis, most of the platelets in the T material lie within 20° of a plane perpendicular to the hot-pressing axis. Therefore, most of the contact angles between platelets must be less than 40° . However, the contact angles for the S composite have a much wider range since the orientation distribution is much more random. It is interesting to note that P and S samples present very similar overall textures even though at a microscale the textures are very different as shown in figure 1.

Figure 2. Orientation distribution of SiC platelets in the 30vol% composites.

¹ Approximately 2/3 of them. Determined by neutron diffraction at AECL, Chalk River Laboratories.

HIGH TEMPERATURE TESTING

The samples were machined into 4x3x45mm bars for flexure creep and 3x4x8mm bars for compression creep. All were machined to a finish according to the ASTM standard C1161-90. Flexure and compression creep tests were done in air at 1250°C at stresses ranging from 7.5 to 80 MPa for flexure, and 33.5 and 43MPa for compression. For the flexure tests, the applied stress and strain were calculated according to Hollenberg et al.[8].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Curves of strain versus time for the different composites are shown in figure 3. The high temperature behaviour of the 30 vol% S material presents a stage of relatively rapid creep followed by a decrease in strain rate of one or two orders of magnitude. Since these two parts are linear a steady state creep rate was assigned to each and was later used to calculate the creep exponent n for each of the regimes. The decrease in strain rate does not seem to depend on the strain or the stress, but, it does depend on the time. It appears after about 1.5×10^5 sec (about two days). This was clearly shown by an annealing experiment in which a sample was annealed at 1250°C for 1.5×10^5 sec and then crept. The results are presented in figure 4. The creep rate of the sample was that expected of a similar sample after two days of creep, suggesting that, the reduction in creep rate is dependent only in time at temperature. It is important to note that the rest of the S composites exhibit a continuous reduction in creep rate with time.

Figure 3. Typical creep curves for 30vol% T, P and S composites.

The strain vs time curves of the T and P materials show a relatively steady reduction of creep rate with time. In these materials it was never possible to achieve steady-state creep conditions. The creep rate reported on the strain rate versus stress plots is rather the lowest creep rate attained after 7 days of testing or the lowest strain rate before the sample failed. The creep data for all the composites is presented in figure 5. The pure alumina exhibits a different creep behaviour depending on the fabrication method used. This suggests a strong influence on the creep behaviour of minor contaminants due to different processing routes. With the experimental conditions used, the pure alumina tends to be more creep resistant than the composites with the exception of the second linear regime in the 30 vol% SiC S composite and 5 vol% SiC T at low stresses.

Figure 4. Annealing the sample (30vol%SiC) reduces the initial creep rate.

Figure 5.5 Strain rate vs stress curves for creep deformation; a) 30vol%SiC S, T and P composites; b) 0, 5 and 15% SiC S and T composites.

Neutron diffraction experiments were done on the 30vol%SiC T and S samples to measure some of the internal strains present in the two phases, alumina and silicon carbide. It was found that the overall compressive (SiC) and tensile (Al_2O_3) strains were the same for the as processed T and S composites. However, the broadening of the diffraction peaks strongly suggests the presence of higher bending strains in the platelet network of the S composite than in the T network. This is probably due to the morphology of the network and the contact angles formed by the platelets as described in the experimental section. These bending strains seem to be relieved after creep, which could contribute to the reduction in creep rate. Although, not measured, the bending strains in the P composite are expected to be very similar to those in the T composite since the contact angles between platelets are very similar except at the boundaries between granules where the contact angles are probably more similar to the S composite.

TEM observations were performed on as-processed and crept 30vol%SiC T and S composites. The latter were crept for 7 days at 33.5MPa in compression. The thickness of the glass layer at the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}$ interface was larger in the T composite than in the S material, both before and after creep, as shown in figure 6. The glass phase likely facilitated grain boundary sliding and cavity formation in the T composite during creep. This is shown in figure 7. Some other differences in impurities were found such as Sulfur at the grain boundaries in the S material (likely due to the use of plaster of paris for slip casting), Fe-Zr or Fe particles at grain boundaries in the S composite and Fe-Ti or Fe particles at grain boundaries in the T composite. We can only speculate that the presence of these particles and impurities affects the creep behaviour of the composites.

Figure 6. Differences in the glass layer thickness at the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}$ interface, a) T as-processed, b) S as processed, c) T after creep and d) S after creep.

Figure 7. The cavity density after creep is higher in the T composite (a) than in the S composite (b).

SUMMARY

Three different processing routes were used to fabricate Al_2O_3 and Al_2O_3/SiC composites which have different platelet network morphologies and internal strains, as well as different impurities. The creep behaviour of the materials varies according to the green processing routes used to fabricate them. The P and T composites behave very similarly, whereas the S material differs significantly. In particular, the 30vol% SiC S composite exhibits a reduction in creep rate of one to two orders of magnitude that is time dependent as demonstrated by an annealing experiment. From TEM observations, the thickness of the glass phase between alumina and silicon carbide grains varies also according to the processing route used. The presence of a thicker layer seems to promote cavitation in the T composite. An explanation for the higher creep rates in the composites as compared with the monolith cannot be provided with the information attained to date.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank Drs. John Root and Ian Swainson from AECL, Chalk River Laboratories and Connie Barry and Michael Gharghoury from McMaster University for their assistance. This work was made possible by a grant from the Ontario Centre for Materials Research.

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